

The Unjournal

Evaluation Summary and Metrics: "Does online fundraising increase charitable giving? A nationwide field experiment on Facebook"

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ABSTRACT

We organized two evaluations of the paper: “Does online fundraising increase charitable giving? A nationwide field experiment on Facebook” [\[1\]](#). To read these evaluations, please see the links below.

Evaluations

1. E1: [Tabaré Capitán](#)
2. E2: [David Reiley](#)

Overall ratings

We asked evaluators to provide overall assessments as well as ratings for a range of specific criteria.

I. Overall assessment (See footnote¹)

II. Journal rank tier, normative rating (0-5): On a ‘scale of journals’, what ‘quality of journal’ should this be published in?² *Note: 0= lowest/none, 5= highest/best.*

	Overall assessment (0-100)	Journal rank tier, normative rating (0-5)
Tabaré Capitán	92	4.8
David Reiley	90	4.5

See “[Metrics](#)” below for a more detailed breakdown of the evaluators’ ratings across several categories. To see these ratings in the context of all Unjournal ratings, with some analysis, see our [data presentation here](#).³

See [here](#) for the current full evaluator guidelines, including further explanation of the requested ratings.

Evaluation summaries**Tabaré Capitán**

This is a large-scale, well-executed field experiment on Facebook ads for charitable giving in Germany. Randomized at the postal code level, the study finds that the campaign increased donations both short- and medium-term, without reducing future giving to the same charity—but possibly crowding out donations to others. Content and delivery method had no differential effect. The design is strong and materials are fully replicable.

David Reiley

The experiment is a well-designed example of geographic randomization to measure the treatment effects of an advertising campaign.

The authors demonstrate a marginally significant ATE. They also demonstrate large, positive, significant spillover effects across geographically close postal codes, indicating that their ATE is a lower bound on the truth. I would like to see more exploration of this result, because it is a surprisingly large effect.

I love that the authors measure the final outcome of actual donations made, instead of some intermediate proxy, because I am never confident that a proxy actually tells us what researchers want it to tell us about final outcomes. But I think the authors might be more careful to present confidence intervals and point out how much statistical uncertainty they have in their estimates.

Metrics

Ratings

[See here](#) for details on the categories below, and the guidance given to evaluators.

	Evaluator 1 Tabaré Capitán			Evaluator 2 David Reiley		
Rating category	Rating (0-100)	90% CI (0-100)*	Comments	Rating (0-100)	90% CI (0-100)*	Comments
Overall assessment ⁴	92	(85, 95)		90	(85, 95)	5
Claims, strength, characterization of evidence ⁶	85	(80, 90)		85	(80, 90)	7
Advancing knowledge and practice ⁸	90	(80, 95)	9	90	(80, 95)	10

Methods: Justification, reasonableness, validity, robustness ¹¹	97	(95, 99)		90	(85, 94)	12
Logic & communication 13	92	(90, 95)		93	(90, 98)	14
Open, collaborative, replicable ¹⁵	97	(93, 100)		92	(88, 95)	16
Real-world relevance 17 , 18	N/A	N/A		90	(80, 94)	19
Relevance to global priorities ²⁰ , 21	N/A	N/A		90	(80, 94)	

Journal ranking tiers

[See here](#) for more details on these tiers.

	Evaluator 1 Tabaré Capitán		Evaluator 2 David Reiley		
Judgment	Ranking tier (0-5)	90% CI	Ranking tier (0-5)	90% CI	Comments

On a 'scale of journals', what 'quality of journal' <i>should</i> this be published in?	4.8	(4.6, 5.0)	4.5	(3.9, 4.7)	22
See here for more details on these tiers.	<p><i>We summarize these as:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 0.0: Marginally respectable/Little to no value • 1.0: OK/Somewhat valuable • 2.0: Marginal B-journal/Decent field journal • 3.0: Top B-journal/Strong field journal • 4.0: Marginal A-Journal/Top field journal • 5.0: A-journal/Top journal 				

Claim identification and assessment (summary)

For the full discussions, see the corresponding sections in each linked evaluation.

	Main research claim ²³	Belief in claim ²⁴	Suggested robustness checks ²⁵	Important 'implication', policy, credibility ²⁶
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<p>Evaluator 1 Tabaré Capitán</p>	<p>Abstract: However, we also found some crowding out of donations to other similar charities or projects. Table 3 shows a negative change in revenue in 23 other similar charities in response to the exogenous variation created by the campaign. It is particularly important because, according to the authors, there is a belief in this literature that charities are complements. In other words, a new donor is good news for everyone. In contrast, this result imply competition. If this is the case, then any funds spent on fundraising may be simply re-distributing a fixed cake (and making it smaller).</p>	<p>Like 90%. They don't have the same level of data quality as their main dataset, but it is very comprehensive.</p>		
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<p>Evaluator 2 David Reiley</p>	<p>The most stunning result in the paper is the measurement of huge geographic spillovers in a geo-randomized advertising experiment on Facebook in Germany. The secondary question about spillovers shows an indirect effect (the effect of treating neighboring postal codes) that is ten times higher than the direct effect (the effect of treating one's own postal code).</p>	<p>I think the claim is probably true, but I worry that it may be exaggerated by the choice of functional form. I cannot find any concrete reason I expect the claim to be false, but the spillover effects seem implausibly huge to me.</p>	<p>I would like to know whether the huge result is robust to different variations on the arbitrary assumptions chosen by the authors. Differences in the distance threshold. Allowing the spillover effect to vary continuously with distance, rather than being a step function that is "on" if the neighboring postal code is within 30km and "off" otherwise. Modeling the spillover effect not just as proportional to the share of treated neighboring postal codes, but as proportional to the share of population that was treated in the neighboring postal codes.</p>	<p>If true, the spillover claim means that the Facebook ad campaign might be much more effective than what was measured in the main average treatment effect. If this is a generally true phenomenon in digital advertising, it means that folks are generally underestimating the effects of advertising with geo-experiments, so ad campaigns might be a lot more effective (3x, 5x, 10x) than has been typically measured in advertising experiments.</p>
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Evaluation manager's discussion

The evaluations for "Does online fundraising increase charitable giving?" demonstrate a close reading of the key claims in the paper as well as the methods (and assumptions) required to substantiate the findings related to those claims. While we did not give any explicit direction to evaluators on what to examine in this paper, the choice of evaluators was driven mainly by the concern of getting to both methodological as well as conceptual issues related to the paper. This bears out in the two evaluations we received.

Tabare Capitan's (E1) evaluation generally aligns with feedback typical for a late-stage paper in applied economics (i.e., one that is "nearly there", potentially accepted for publication at a "top" journal, as in the case of this paper). However, the evaluation highlights a larger question around reporting standards in such large-scale experiments that are done typically in partnership with non-profits or charitable organizations. One

relates to reports around profitability of such demonstrably effective campaigns. How should we deal with statistical imprecision in such estimates? (This issue was also raised by E2, David Reiley). A related issue flagged here is that advertising on online platforms is highly dynamic, and tech platforms may shift goalposts considerably, potentially rendering any estimate around costs of such ad campaigns as parameters that might need to be revisited according to the context and timing of the study. Finally, the evaluation raises two more questions in an illuminating fashion, that almost all randomized experiments (and experimenters) need to grapple with: (a) external validity (i.e., are the results informative about charitable giving in Germany, outside Germany, in child-centric sectors of giving?) and (b) reporting results “of” randomization, which rather than simply reporting on balance between observable covariates, perhaps also need to be constructed to report standardized differences in covariates. [Tagat mentioned similar concerns in his pre-evaluation notes, see footnote.²⁷]

David Reiley’s (E2) evaluation is one of the most comprehensive evaluations I have come across, reflecting a deep engagement with work in this domain, both from the perspective of a researcher studying charitable giving, but also from someone with the practical experience of having worked in the sector. I will not go into depth into each aspect of his evaluation, as any researcher interested in working in this domain should read this (as well as E1) very carefully to get pointers on how best to design and test such campaigns. It covers everything from investigating the (non-pre-registered) treatment of the outcome variable (trimming, winsorizing etc.) to other deviations from the pre-registration plan. While certain logistical challenges (especially in the world outside academia, e.g., charitable organizations) are bound to come up, E2 makes a strong case for justifying why, where, when, and how these deviations can affect reporting standards and outcomes in field experiments.

Reiley’s evaluation also requested clarifications on the geographical spillovers (which I also flagged in my initial notes on the paper, see footnote²⁸) – these were addressed in the authors’ responses. Reiley’s evaluation also carefully walks the reader through various issues in randomization inference, heterogenous treatment effects, and other measurement issues with the care of a university professor but the passion of an ardent practitioner working to get this right. This is both rare and incredibly useful in the field of economics, and I am grateful that Reiley’s evaluation covers this in great detail.

My own takeaway from these evaluations is that they provide rigorous insight into the kind of work that economists set out to do in partnership with a wide array of organizations (even if this particular paper is only related to charitable giving, it does speak at length about what kind of advertising is effective in raising giving). There are various practical, methodological, and technical challenges that researchers need to take into account, carefully weighing the tradeoffs between them and greater (or lower) causal inference.

Unjournal process notes

COI Issues

David Reinstein played a role in prioritizing this paper for evaluation, and his [own research agenda](#) includes several papers considering questions addressed in this paper, including the competition between charities, and the effect of quantitative impact information on donor choices. However, five other members of our team also voted in favor of prioritizing this paper for evaluation.

As co-director of the journal, David Reinstein tried to take a hands-off/arms-length approach to this evaluation, although he was in some contact with Anirudh Tagat, the evaluation manager, and in correspondence with David Reiley during the final stages of this evaluation process.

Tabaré Capitan (evaluator 1) is a member of our Field Specialist team. however, he did not play a role in prioritizing this paper for evaluation.

Why we chose this paper

From our prioritization discussion and other threads, considering the potential for impact on global priorities.

The issue of the “crowding-out” of fundraising is important and still unresolved. The design appears strong (variation at the postal code level), potentially pretty close to a gold standard for studying this. Seems to contain some methodological contributions to field experimental work relevant to impactful charitable giving. Possible downsides: not obvious how the mere ‘existence’ of crowding out (which is probably the conventional wisdom) yields impactful actionable insights, and the results here might not be generalizable to other charity pairings/asks of more interest. Still, this arguably presents the strongest/most relevant evidence about this. E.g., Save the Children is a development charity.

My impression was that this presented some of the most credible evidence on the impact of Facebook ads and on crowding out/substitution in the context of charitable giving for global poverty. The ‘geo-randomization’ approach is particularly compelling.

Authors’ engagement

The authors were aware of this evaluation process but decided not to respond extensively, for compelling personal reasons. Also highlighted two fairly small points meriting correction in David Reiley’s report. Excerpting their response letter:

The length and thoroughness of their evaluations clearly demonstrate the significant time and intellectual effort they invested in engaging deeply with our research. We are truly grateful for their insightful and constructive comments, which reflect a genuine commitment to advancing the quality and impact of research in this important field.

We also express our sincere appreciation to the editors of The Unjournal... Their support made this valuable dialogue possible and highlighted new perspectives on our work.

Since our paper has already been published in *Management Science*, we do not intend to provide a detailed point-by-point response at this stage. Nevertheless, we find the evaluators' suggestions and reflections very valuable and will carefully consider them as we continue our research agenda and develop future projects. We welcome this opportunity for public scientific discourse and hope that these evaluations encourage further inquiry and application in the realm of online charitable fundraising.

References

- [1] Adena, Maja, and Anselm Hager. 2025. 'Does Online Fundraising Increase Charitable Giving? A Nationwide Field Experiment on Facebook'. *Management Science* 71 (4): 3216–31.
<https://doi.org/10.1287/mnsc.2020.00596>.

Footnotes

1. We asked them to rank this paper "heuristically" as a percentile "relative to all serious research in the same area that you have encountered in the last three years." We requested they "consider all aspects of quality, credibility, importance to knowledge production, and importance to practice. ↵

2. See ranking tiers discussed [here](#). ↵

3. Note: if you are reading this before, or soon after this has been publicly released, the ratings from this paper may not yet have been incorporated into that data presentation. ↵

4.

Judge the quality of the research heuristically. Consider all aspects of quality, credibility, importance to knowledge production, and importance to practice.

↵

5. I really appreciate seeing a study of advertising that looks at final consumer outcomes. I think the authors have done a nice job. My main complaint is that they oversell some of their statistically insignificant, and marginally significant, results. ↵

6. "Do the authors do a good job of (i) stating their main questions and claims, (ii) providing strong evidence and powerful approaches to inform these, and (iii) correctly characterizing the nature of their evidence?"

This was on the newer form only ↵

7. My main complaint is in relying too much on point estimates, and not providing enough confidence-interval estimates for the more subtle results (beyond measurement of the overall average treatment effect). [↵](#)

8.

To what extent does the project contribute to the field or to practice, particularly in ways that are directly or indirectly relevant to global priorities and impactful interventions?

[↵](#)

9. I am not familiar enough with this field for my answer to matter. Based on what the authors claim, big contribution. [↵](#)

10. The measurement of large spillover effects is really interesting. In future work, I would like to see the authors go into more detail on this analysis, because the spillovers seem surprisingly high (average indirect effect nearly 10x larger than the direct effect). I wonder how robust these results are to different choices of functional-form specification. It might be fruitful to pursue the observed dominance of urban-to-rural spillovers. And if the indirect effects are really so much higher than the direct effects, I would love to know why that's the case. Can we find direct, corroborating evidence that a huge number of people in the sample live in rural postal codes but work in nearby urban postal codes, for example? I could imagine writing an entire paper to explore this phenomenon and better understand it. [↵](#)

11. Are methods clearly justified and explained? Are methods and their underlying assumptions reasonable? Are the results likely to be robust to changes in the assumptions? Have the authors avoided bias and questionable research practices? [↵](#)

12. The experimental design and analysis is well explained. [↵](#)

13. Are concepts clearly defined? Is the reasoning transparent? Are conclusions consistent with the evidence (or formal proofs) presented? Are the data and/or analysis, including tables and figures, relevant to the argument? [↵](#)

14. This paper is written much more clearly than the average academic paper. I like to think that I helped the authors achieve this positive outcome, as I was a referee on the paper at Management Science. [↵](#)

15.

Would another researcher be able to replicate the analysis? Are the method and its details explained sufficiently? Is the source of the data clear? Is the data made as widely available as possible, with clear labeling and explanation? Do the authors provide resources that are likely to enable future research and meta-analysis?

[↵](#)

16. I have not tried loading the data and running the authors' code, but I verified that it existed on the Management Science website. I also find that the experimental design was described clearly enough that I could try to replicate it, with sufficient budget, on Facebook. [↔](#)

17.

Does the paper consider real-world relevance and deal with policy and implementation questions? Are the setup, assumptions, and focus realistic and relevant to practitioners?

[↔](#)

18.

The latter ratings were merged in the newer form

"Are the paper's chosen topic and approach likely to be useful to global priorities, cause prioritization, and high-impact interventions?"

"Does the paper consider real-world relevance and deal with policy and implementation questions? Are the setup, assumptions, and focus realistic? Do the authors report results that are relevant to practitioners? Do they provide useful quantified estimates (costs, benefits, etc.)?" [↔](#)

19. These results help us understand more about how digital advertising really works, particularly in the realm of charitable fundraising. Scholars learn important ideas from this paper about how to run more successful experiments to measure the effects of advertising, and charitable fundraisers learn ideas about whether Facebook advertising can be profitable as well as how they might improve their ad campaigns. [↔](#)

20. Are the paper's chosen topic and approach likely to be useful to global priorities, cause prioritization, and high-impact interventions? [↔](#)

21.

The latter ratings were merged in the newer form

"Are the paper's chosen topic and approach likely to be useful to global priorities, cause prioritization, and high-impact interventions?"

"Does the paper consider real-world relevance and deal with policy and implementation questions? Are the setup, assumptions, and focus realistic? Do the authors report results that are relevant to practitioners? Do they provide useful quantified estimates (costs, benefits, etc.)?" [↔](#)

22. This has already been published at Management Science. [↔](#)

23.

The evaluator was given the following instructions:

Identify the most important and impactful factual claim this research makes – e.g., a binary claim or a point estimate or prediction.

Please state the authors' claim precisely and quantitatively. Identify the source of the claim (i.e., cite the paper), and briefly mention the evidence underlying this. We encourage you to explain why you believe this claim is important, either here, or in the text of your report. [↵](#)

24. Evaluators were asked: To what extent do you **believe** the claim you stated above? Feel free to express this either a. in terms of the probability of the claim being true, b. as a credible interval for the parameter being estimated, or c. however you feel comfortable. [↵](#)

25.

We asked:

[Optional] What additional information, evidence, replication, or robustness check would make you substantially more (or less) confident in this claim?

Feel free to refer to the main body of your evaluation here; you don't need to repeat yourself. Please specify how you would perform this robustness check (etc.) as precisely as you are willing. E.g., if you suggest a particular estimation command in a statistical package, this could be very helpful for future robustness replication work. [↵](#)

26.

We asked:

[Optional] Identify the important **implication** of the above claim for funding and policy choices? To what extent do you **believe** this implication? How should it inform policy choices?

Note: this 'implication' could be suggested by the evaluation manager in some cases. As an example of an 'implication' ... in a global health context, the 'main claim' might suggest that a vitamin supplement intervention, if scaled up, would save lives at a \$XXXX per life saved.

We did not ask this in the 'applied stream' as it is most likely redundant.

[↵](#)

27.

Tagat: "The paper could do more comprehensive statistical tests for pretreatment differences. While Table 1 shows no significant differences in Save the Children donations, this analysis is incomplete: (a) Table A2 is referenced but doesn't include p-values or clear difference tests; For competing charity analysis (Table A4), significant pretreatment differences are acknowledged, requiring difference-in-difference specifications; and (b) The crowding-out analysis reveals baseline imbalances that necessitate additional statistical controls."

"Although the paper is already published (in a reputed journal), the study would benefit from addressing the pretreatment balance documentation, clarifying geographic measurement issues, and providing more detailed methodology for handling potential contamination effects."

↩

28.

Tagat's notes: "The 30km radius for measuring spillovers seems to be coarse for an online platform study. This might be because spillovers in the online domain are especially difficult to track. Online sharing capabilities (video forwarding) could extend treatment effects beyond geographic boundaries, control group postal codes might receive shared content through social networks. Although the paper mentions "forwarding button" functionality, it doesn't adequately address cross-contamination between treatment and control areas".

↩

References

1. Adena, Maja, and Anselm Hager. 2025. 'Does Online Fundraising Increase Charitable Giving? A Nationwide Field Experiment on Facebook'. *Management Science* 71 (4): 3216–31. <https://doi.org/10.1287/mnsc.2020.00596>. ↩